

Additional file 6: Explanatory statements that participants mentioned for their choice of yes/neutral/no considering a second ultrasound-guided lymph node biopsy or encouraging another to do so

Clarifying statement for second participation when answered yes, no or neutral	Clarifying statement for encouraging others to participate when answered yes, no or neutral
<u>Yes</u>	<u>Yes</u>
<p>The biopsy went 100% better than I expected beforehand</p> <p>It was less painful than expected</p> <p>Biopsy was not painful and it is important for research</p> <p>If it aids medicine in finding a cure</p> <p>A second biopsy would not be a problem</p> <p>It went better than expected</p> <p>The value for future patients outweighs the little pain and discomfort I endured</p> <p>I have experienced no problems with the biopsy</p> <p>(I would not do it to have fun,) but if necessary, no problem</p> <p>I barely felt it and it is for a very good cause</p> <p>If it is necessary for research</p> <p>I would for research</p> <p>I do not mind. It does not hurt, so I would undergo a second biopsy</p> <p>If it is important for research</p> <p>If it is necessary for further research</p> <p>If it contributes to knowledge about RA, I would consider it</p> <p>The procedure was not too painful and doable</p> <p>The procedure went fine. I did experience some pain, but they immediately responded to that</p>	<p>I would explain that a biopsy seems way worse than it actually is</p> <p>It is for a good cause</p> <p>I have already encouraged another</p> <p>We should help each other</p> <p>Because others can benefit from it</p> <p>Only if this person is mentally and physically up to undergo the procedure and feels the personal need to contribute to research</p> <p>Because research is very important</p> <p>To understand more about the disease. The general benefit is also very important.</p> <p>As humans we should help each other</p> <p>If the study is of great importance</p>

<u>Neutral</u>	<u>Neutral</u>
<p>It depends on the study goal and necessity of the study</p> <p>It depends the goal of the study</p> <p>Only if it is really needed</p> <p>Currently, I experience too much pain from RA so two study participations is enough for me</p> <p>I would do it to benefit research</p>	<p>Everyone should decide for themselves</p> <p>I do not know anyone with RA , so I do not know who to ask</p> <p>Depends on the goal of the study</p> <p>I would not know who</p> <p>Everyone should decide for themselves</p> <p>I would describe my experience and leave the decision up to that person</p>
<u>No</u>	<u>No</u>
<p>Very painful</p> <p>Once is enough</p>	<p>Very painful experience</p> <p>Because the people I know, would not do it</p>